

TEMPERATURE DEPENDENT RHEOLOGICAL PROPERTIES OF ULTRA-THIN CHOPPED CARBON FIBER TAPE REINFORCED THERMOPLASTICS

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Abstract

Ultra-thin chopped carbon fiber tape reinforced thermoplastics (UT-CTT), one type of discontinuous carbon fiber reinforced thermoplastics (CFRTP), shows great potential for light-weight structures of automobiles for its excellent formability and relatively high mechanical properties. As a type randomly oriented strands (ROS) composites, compression molding of UT-CTT is the process that enables it to form various shapes and structures. In this paper, a new method for measuring viscosities of UT-CTT during its forming process is employed and a viscosity model based on microstructure of UT-CTT is established. The model was then compared with the measurement results of viscosities of UT-CTT at two different temperatures. The results show that two distinctive regions are identified: a linear viscoelastic region and a transition region that is partially frictional and viscous. This study aims to obtain better understanding of inter-ply mechanisms during compression molding of ROS composites and improve prediction of squeeze flow behavior of UT-CTT.

1 INTRODUCTION

Carbon fiber reinforced thermoplastics (CFRTP) have been regarded as an excellent material for lightweight applications, and it is suitable for automotive manufacturing industry. Ultra-thin chopped carbon fiber tape reinforced thermoplastics (UT-CTT), one type of CFRTP, have advantages in both forming applications for complex components and mechanical properties being comparable to quasi-isotropic continuous fiber laminates [1]. Therefore, expanding of UT-CTT applications in automotive industry would positively contribute to mitigate fossil fuel consumption and global warming by enhancing the fuel efficiency of vehicles.

The UT-CTT can be classified as randomly oriented strands (ROS) due to the structural characteristics of the material. During compression molding of ROS composites, which is the typical process method for UT-CTT, it is assumed that three governing deformation mechanisms occur: packing stress, squeeze flow (macro-scopic and meso-scopic) and inter-ply friction [2]. The packing stress corresponds to an elastic compaction behavior of the material at low load, causing from bending and conformation of the strands. The squeeze flow relates to the melt flows at the macroscopic scale that fill the mold cavity, as well as transverse deformation of each strand under an applied pressure. The inter-ply shear mechanism is governed by the friction coefficient between two plies or strands sliding on each other, also influenced by forming process parameters such as sliding velocity and normal pressure.

In previous studies, most researchers use a parallel-platen approach to measure the compression molding process for different materials [3]. However, the inter-ply friction cannot be distinguished from squeeze flow by the result of this method. Moreover, for materials with a yield stress (including UT-CTT), the measurement of the yield stress in parallel-platen approach is difficult to establish precisely [4]. Therefore,

a new method that can directly measure the inter-ply friction and yield stress, as well as other deformation mechanisms that leads to a better understanding of the compression molding process of UT-CTT is expected.

2 MATERIALS AND PROCESSES

2.1 Materials

UT-CTT were made from ultra-thin unidirectional (UD) CF/PA6 prepreg sheet. This sheet was provided by Industrial Technology Center of Fukui Prefecture. Spread carbon fiber tow (TR 50S, Mitsubishi Rayon Co. LTD.) and Polyamid-6 (PA6, DIAMIRON™ C, Mitsubishi Plastics, Inc.) are used to manufacture the sheet. During manufacturing, film type of PA6 and parallel continuous carbon fibers were compressed at high temperature to form the sheet. The thin sheet thickness (44 μm in average) assures good in-plane and parallel orientation of the fibers. The sheet was then cut by an automated cut machine and a hand-cutter mold into chopped tapes with 6 mm in length and 5 mm in width. A wet-type paper making process for fabricating intermediate chopped tapes sheets was employed to make good in-plane orientation of the tapes. The intermediate sheets were molded at 250 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ under the pressure of 5 MPa in a compression molding machine. The fiber volume fraction (V_f) of fabricated UT-CTT is 55% in average. Total procedures for fabricating UT-CTT are shown in Fig.1.

Figure 1: Overview of CTT fabrication procedures.

The neat polymer specimen of PA6 was fabricated by a hand truder using the same film type of PA6 in the UT-CTT manufacturing process (DIAMIRON™ C, Mitsubishi Plastics, Inc.). PA6 films were heated at 260 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 5 min, then pushed into a mold at 100 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ and cooled down to form the desired dimension.

2.2 Experiments

A stress-controlled MCR 302 rheometer (Anton Paar Inc.) with parallel plate accessory was employed for angular frequency test and stress ramp test in oscillatory shear mode. This accessory is composed of two circular aluminum plates with 20 mm diameter. Heated nitrogen gas flowed into a convection chamber in order to induce nitrogen blanket for the measurement. Polymer rheology measurements for PA6 were conducted under angular frequency ranged from 10^{-1} to 100 rad/s with strain amplitude of 1% at two

temperatures: 240 °C and 260 °C. The yield stress of UT-CTT was measured under shear stress ranged from 10 kPa to 30 kPa with an angular frequency of 1 rad/s. The tests of suspension rheology measurement of UT-CTT were implemented by modulating an angular frequency range from 10⁻¹ to 100 rad/s at different strain amplitudes from 0.05 to 10%. All measurements for UT-CTT were also conducted at 240 °C and 260 °C respectively.

2.3 Modeling methods

Two types of Generalized Newtonian Fluids (GNF) models were used to functional fitting the viscosities of PA6: the Carreau model

$$\eta_p(\dot{\gamma}) = \eta_0 [1 + (\lambda\dot{\gamma})^2]^{\frac{(n-1)}{2}} \quad (1)$$

and the Cross model

$$\eta_p(\dot{\gamma}) = \eta_0 / \left[1 + \left(\frac{\eta_0}{\tau^*} \dot{\gamma} \right)^{n-1} \right] \quad (2)$$

Linear-viscoelastic region (LVR) of polymer melts was assumed to be below 1% of strain under the shear. Since, Cox-Merz rule was applied to transform angular frequency to shear rate:

$$\eta(\dot{\gamma}) = |\eta^*(\omega)| \quad \text{for } \dot{\gamma} = \omega \quad (3)$$

For UT-CTT, based on the former research, three forces were found occurring at the contact points between fibers [5]. This can be presented as

$$\sigma \approx \sigma^{(p)} = \frac{1}{V} \sum_{\text{fibers}} \sum_{\text{contact points}} (\mathbf{f}_n + \mathbf{f}_f + \mathbf{f}_h) \mathbf{x} \quad (4)$$

where the friction force \mathbf{f}_f is proportional to the normal force \mathbf{f}_n

$$\mathbf{f}_f = k_f \overline{|\mathbf{f}_n|} v^{-1} \mathbf{v} \quad (5)$$

The hydrodynamic lubrication force \mathbf{f}_h can be expressed as

$$\mathbf{f}_h = k_f \eta_p \frac{\mathbf{v}}{\alpha} \quad (6)$$

where η_p is the viscosity of the neat polymer melt and α is the average thickness of the polymer film present around the contact points.

In UT-CTT, however, there are two position status for all fibers: position that on the tape surface and position that is not on the tape surface. At the second type of position, all fibers are parallel to each other within the same tape. In this study, we assume that $\mathbf{f}_f = \mathbf{f}_h = 0$ in this situation, since local shear caused by friction force and lubrication force is difficult to occur between parallel fibers. Consequently, the shear stress τ becomes

$$\tau = \begin{cases} N^i \alpha (|\mathbf{f}_f| + |\mathbf{f}_h|), & \text{at tape surface} \\ 0, & \text{not at tape surface} \end{cases} \quad (7)$$

where N^i is the number of interaction points per unit volume for the fibers at the first type of position

$$N^i = \frac{16f\phi^2}{\pi^2 a^3} \quad (8)$$

and a is fiber diameter.

Thus, combining fibers at both types of positions, the stress can be expressed as (use the Cross model for η_p as an example)

$$\tau = k_f S(t) P + k_h S(t) \cdot \frac{16}{\pi^2 a \alpha} f \Phi^2 \eta_0 \dot{\gamma} / \left[1 + \left(\frac{a \eta_0}{\alpha \tau^*} \dot{\gamma} \right)^{n-1} \right] \quad (8)$$

where $S(t)$ is the ratio of numbers of fibers at the first type of position to all fibers, which is related to tape thickness t of UT-CTT.

The steady-state shear viscosity can then be calculated following the equation

$$\eta_{sp} = \frac{\tau}{\dot{\gamma}} \quad (9)$$

Since in this study, UT-CTT is measured under oscillatory shear mode instead of steady-state shear, Rutgers-Delaware relationship [6], regarded as an extended Cox-Merz rule for concentrated suspensions, is employed, which describes that for certain materials (including UT-CTT that meets the requirements), the steady-state viscosity η could be superposed on complex viscosity $|\eta^*|$ as a function of effective shear rate:

$$|\eta^*(\gamma_m \omega)| = \eta(\dot{\gamma}) \quad (10)$$

This suggests that the viscosity can be rewritten in the form

$$|\eta_{sp}^*| = \tau_Y (\gamma_m \omega)^{-1} + k_h S(t) \cdot \frac{16}{\pi^2 a \alpha} f \Phi^2 \eta_0 / \left[1 + \left(\frac{a \eta_0}{\alpha \tau^*} \gamma_m \omega \right)^{n-1} \right] \quad (11)$$

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Results of out-of-plane shear viscosities of PA6 polymer matrix is shown in Fig. 2. Using Cox-Merz rule, the values of angular frequency were converted to shear rate for the measured viscosities. The shear rate range of measurements is chosen regarding actual process situation; the upper limit of measurements may be appropriate since the compression molding procedure has relatively low upper limit of shear rate. The measurement results in each temperature were averaged among three repetitive experiments. Results showed that the Carreau model and the Cross model all provide precise illustrations of shear viscosity curve of the polymer melts in the shear rate range. The upper Newtonian region and shear thinning region can be observed in the curves of both viscosity results and the GNF models in the shear rate range of this study. Parameters in these models could be achievable by functional fitting to the experimental results as given in Table 1.

Figure 2: Viscosities of PA6 in different temperatures and functional fitting to GNF models.

Table 1: Rheological parameters for GNF models.

	The Carreau model			The Cross model		
	η_0 (Pa·s)	λ (s)	n	η_0 (Pa·s)	τ^* (Pa)	n
240 °C	1202	0.26	0.84	1247	1.67×10^5	1.6
260 °C	789	0.42	0.85	863	1.00×10^5	1.43

In both models, the zero shear viscosity η_0 represents for the initial viscosity value in upper Newtonian region, and n is the power-law index which decides the decrease rate of viscosities in shear thinning region. The relaxation time λ in the Carreau model and critical stress τ^* in the cross model both represents for the onset of shear thinning region. The relaxation time λ is in negative correlation with the onset of shear thinning region, while the critical stress τ^* is in positive correlation. From the results, it was observed that in both models, at the lower temperature (240 °C), the zero shear viscosity η_0 showed bigger value than it at the higher temperature (260 °C), and onset of shear thinning region fell at the bigger shear rate at the higher temperature (shown as smaller λ and bigger τ^* in these two models). It was also found that there is no apparent tendency of power-law index in different temperatures.

Although both models shows good agreement with viscosity results, underestimation of the viscosities using the Carreau model in low shear rate region is observed. Thus, the cross model is used for modeling viscosity properties of PA6 and implemented for the viscosity model of UT-CTT.

The results of stress ramp tests of UT-CTT at 240 °C and 260 °C are shown in Fig. 3. All results shows two distinctive curve segments and revealed the certain existence of a yield stress of UT-CTT. The first

curve segment indicates linear tendency below the yield stress governed by packing geometry and Coulombic friction force. Then, transformation of slope reveals the beginning of shear flow caused by hydrodynamic lubrication force. The yield stress value was determined by using the first derivative function of the viscosity results. The point at which its first derivative value decreases at the largest degree among all former points with less shear stress was determined to be the yield point. Yield stress evaluation results are shown in Table 2.

Figure 3: Yield stress evaluation of UT-CTT ((A), (B), (C) are repetitive experiments at 240 °C, and (D), (E), (F) are repetitive experiments at 260 °C).

Table 2: Yield stress values of UT-CTT suspensions.

	Yield stress values (kPa)			Average (kPa)
	240 °C	23.9	20.4	25.2
260 °C	23.5	20.8	25.6	23.3

The results reveals that for UT-CTT, the yield stress shows equivalent levels both at 240 °C and 260 °C. This suggests that there is no obvious difference of Coulombic friction force at these two different temperatures. Since the measurements were conducted under similar normal pressures, it can be thus concluded that the frictional coefficient is not significantly affected by varying temperatures in this study.

Fig. 4 (a) and (b) shows the results of angular frequency tests of UT-CTT at 240 °C and 260 °C, respectively, under different strain amplitudes from 0.05%-10%. Linear relationship between complex viscosity and angular frequency was observed, and complex viscosity was found decreasing with increasing strain amplitudes.

Figure 4: Result of angular frequency tests of UT-CTT at (a) 240 °C and (b) 260 °C.

Fig. 5 (a) and (b) shows the complex viscosities at 240 °C and 260 °C, respectively, accounted for the function of effective shear rate, which was defined and calculated as the product of the angular frequency and strain amplitudes at variance strain amplitudes. At both temperatures, two regions of complex viscosities above 3 % strain amplitude were found. The first region with the log-log slope -1 reveals the predominance of a pseudo-solid behavior below the shear rate of 1/s. In this region, the upper Newtonian plateau, which is related to the behavior of polymer matrix, is covered because of the relatively high yield stress. The second region above the shear rate of 1/s indicates viscoelastic behavior caused by Coulombic friction force and hydrodynamic lubrication force at the same time. In this study, since the melted UT-CTT are highly concentrated fiber suspensions, pseudo-liquid behavior cannot dominate the viscosity results even at high effective shear rates. Thus, only slight variation of the slope can be observed.

The solid line in Fig. 5 (a) and (b) show the functional fitting results by Eq. (11). Parameters of the functional fitting are presented in Table 3. The rheological parameters of polymer matrix in the equation are as same as the results showed in Table 1. Precise agreement between complex viscosities above 1/s strain and the functional fitting results can be observed at both two temperatures, illustrating the validity of Eq. (11) to describe viscoelastic behavior of UT-CTT in these conditions. Same lubrication coefficient was found by functional fitting in both temperatures. From the result, it shows that Eq. (11) which is established based on the Rutgers-Delaware relationship can well describe complex viscosities of UT-CTT under oscillatory shear mode.

Table 3: Functional fitting parameters of complex viscosities of UT-CTT.

	Yield stress τ_Y (kPa)	Effective lubrication coefficient $K_h \cdot S(t)$ (μm^2)	Fiber diameter a (μm)	Shear gap α (μm)	Distribution function f (-)	Fiber volume fraction Φ (-)	Zero shear viscosity η_0 (Pa·s)	Critical stress τ^* (kPa)	Power-law index n (-)
240 °C	23.2	144	7	1.88	$2/\pi$	0.55	1247	167	1.6
260 °C	23.3	144	7	1.88	$2/\pi$	0.55	863	100	1.43

(a)

(b)

Figure 5. Complex viscosities as a function of effective shear rate at various strain amplitude at (a) 240 °C and (b) 260 °C.

4 CONCLUSIONS

The temperature dependence of rheological properties of a kind of ROS material, UT-CTT, were measured in this study. A new viscosity model based on microstructural interactions of UT-CTT, such as fiber-fiber interactions and fiber-matrix interactions, was established. A new method was employed for conducting viscosity measurements of UT-CTT by using a rotational rheometer. To testify the feasibility of the model to UT-CTT, the viscosities of polymer matrix and the composite suspension have been measured under oscillatory shear mode. GNF models were found well describe the viscosities of the polymer matrix, and the obtained parameters were combined into the final model. The yield stress of UT-CTT was precisely measured at different temperatures. It was found that the yield stress almost stay at the same value under the two temperatures. The viscosities of UT-CTT as a function of effective shear rate were measured, and two distinctive regions were found above strain amplitude of 3%: a linear viscoelastic region predominated by pseudo-solid behavior at low effective shear rates, and a transition region combining frictional and viscous components together at high effective shear rates. Finally, the complex viscosities of UT-CTT is found being well fitted into the model. It is expected that this study will contribute to better understanding of inter-ply mechanisms during compression molding of ROS composites and improving prediction of squeeze flow behavior of UT-CTT.

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